

Go Fast: GPU Optimizer for FPGA-LUT Approximate Simulation and Tuning

Abstract—This paper introduces Go-Fast, a novel approach that accelerates the simulation and optimization of LUT-based FPGA circuits using GPUs. Unlike previous GPU-based simulators that target general digital circuits with event-driven approaches, Go-Fast employs batch simulation techniques specifically optimized for approximate computing scenarios. The system utilizes both data parallelism to execute testbenches across numerous threads and structural parallelism for simultaneous simulation and logic pruning. Go-Fast fully exploits GPU architectural features by maximizing register usage, minimizing memory access, and allocating more work per thread. This domain-specific approach generates efficient source-to-source CUDA code that achieves significant performance improvements: five orders of magnitude over the Verilator simulator and two to three orders over optimized multi-core implementations.

I. INTRODUCTION

FPGA circuit designers have explored the trade-offs between area and delay, and more recently, power for decades. The basic metrics are the number of lookup tables (LUTs) and the depth of the critical path. However, optimization should preserve the original circuit functionality. With the recent advancement of machine learning techniques, the field has seen the rise of approximate computation methodologies as cost-optimization strategies. These approaches, such as approximate logic synthesis [1]–[3], deliberately introduce minimal computational imprecision in domains that can tolerate errors such as machine learning, resulting in substantial reductions in circuit area, latency, and energy requirements.

Machine learning approaches use batch simulation to evaluate model accuracy during the training step to fit parameters. Hardware accelerators such as GPUs reduce computation time through parallel execution. For digital circuit simulation, GPUs have shown orders of magnitude acceleration compared to CPU implementations [4]–[15]. However, previous GPU simulators target general digital circuits and exact simulation, allowing further performance improvement for domain-specific scenarios. Similarly, most GPU simulators are event-driven, while batch simulators are more suitable for approximate computing scenarios. Additionally, batch simulation offers more regular parallel optimization opportunities when targeting GPU architectures than the irregular parallelism generated by event-driven approaches.

We introduce Go-Fast - GPU Optimizer for FPGA-LUT Approximate Simulation and Tuning. First, we target domain-specific LUT-based circuits for IoT devices, as computing data on edge enhances energy efficiency and data privacy protection, reduces bandwidth costs, and enables low-latency response [16]. Second, in the training step, we explore GPU

data and structural parallelism in simulation scenarios. Data parallelism enables concurrent testbench execution using numerous threads to simulate target circuits. Structural parallelism facilitates simultaneous simulation and logic pruning. Our GPU implementation maximizes register utilization, minimizes memory accesses, and allocates increased workloads per thread to exploit GPU high-performance capabilities, resulting in accelerated simulators.

We organize this paper as follows. First, Section II introduces the key features needed to generate efficient GPU code. Section III presents existing GPU circuit simulators and highlights our contributions. Section IV details our approach in two scenarios: circuit simulation and circuit optimization. Section V presents the main results and advances in state-of-the-art. Finally, Section VI draws the main conclusions and outlines future directions to extend this work.

II. BACKGROUND

GPU architectures are suitable for managing hundreds of thousands of threads. However, to fully extract high performance, launching many threads executing simple tasks is not always necessary. It is possible to explore instruction-level parallelism using fewer threads and allocating more tasks to each thread [17].

A GPU contains thousands of arithmetic units or CUDA cores that operate in a pipelined fashion. Since logic operations typically execute in 4-6 clock cycles [18], it is advisable to launch at least four more threads than the number of available computing units (CUDA cores) to maintain full utilization. To optimize performance, developers should focus on increasing instruction-level parallelism by launching sufficient GPU tasks while maximizing register utilization. The optimal thread-to-computing-unit ratio generally falls between 4 and 10, depending on the specific kernel's resource requirements and characteristics.

Although GPUs feature high-throughput memory subsystems, including L1 cache and shared memory, their memory latency remains high (20-30 clock cycles) compared to multi-core CPUs, even in the latest GPU generations [19]. Furthermore, GPUs are not well-suited for event-driven approaches due to performance degradation caused by branch divergence, as they operate on a Single Instruction Multiple Thread (SIMT) model. Therefore, practical GPU implementations should minimize branching code sections and memory access operations.

III. RELATED WORK

In the early 2010s, GPU-based simulators were proposed [4]–[11] that improved CPU-based simulator performance by one or two orders of magnitude.

Recently, new GPU simulators have been developed using graph-based GPU libraries for event-driven simulation or re-simulation approaches [12]–[15] that achieve speedups of two to four orders of magnitude compared to single-core CPUs, and up to three orders of magnitude compared to multi-core CPUs running Verilator [20].

Our proposal differs from previous approaches. First, we focus on batch simulation rather than event-driven simulation. We target medium-sized circuits for low-cost FPGA in edge computing devices, ranging from hundreds to a few thousand LUTs [21], [22], and we target a LUT level simulator. We assign as much work as possible to each thread to maximize performance and local register usage by computing logic instructions while avoiding high-latency memory operations. Our approach can reach up to five orders of magnitude compared to Verilator multi-core implementation [20].

IV. MORE WORK PER THREAD

Figure 1 depicts the Go-Fast proposal. An approximate logic synthesis tool requires a fast simulator engine to validate its decisions. In general, an iterative cycle of ‘optimize, simulate, optimize, simulate’ repeats multiple times, which requires a fast simulator. Section IV-A describes our GPU-based simulator, and Section IV-B presents a proof of concept, where we include a parallel greedy pruning approach in the GPU code to demonstrate the flexibility of our proposal. This work paves the way for future work to incorporate more aggressive pruning approaches [2], [23]–[25] in GPU code.

Fig. 1: Go-Fast Framework for Approximate Logic Synthesis.

A. Parallel LUT Circuit Simulation

Our first contribution is exploring data parallelism to simulate LUT-level circuits on GPUs. The GPU compiler generates more efficient code for logic equation descriptions. Using a stimulus vector to simulate, we explore data parallelism by scheduling a subset of the stimulus vector for each thread, utilizing the more work-per-thread approach [17]. Each thread executes a complete circuit simulation: reading the inputs, computing the intermediate LUT values, and propagating them to the outputs. By assigning more work per thread, we maximize local GPU register usage and avoid thread synchronization since there is no circuit partitioning.

Each thread processes 32 samples simultaneously for every test point p by encoding them as a single 32-bit integer and applying bitwise operations. Additionally, we utilize the

GPU’s parallel capabilities to generate random stimuli while avoiding memory operations.

B. Parallel Approximate LUT Optimization

Recently, approximate logic synthesis approaches [24] have become an interesting option to optimize machine learning implementations. Our second contribution is embedding a pruning approach in GPU simulator code. As a proof of concept, we implement a greedy design exploration methodology using random LUT pruning (stuck at 0 or 1). Further work could include genetic algorithms, k-input pruning [24], or probabilistic approaches [2], [25].

Our focus in this work is to illustrate the potential of integrating GPU simulation into the design of approximate logic synthesis (ALS) for multi-level circuits targeting LUT FPGAs. In this direction, it is possible to integrate other local approximation changes (LACs) easily. We implement a parallel evaluation where each thread simulates the entire circuit with a different pruning configuration. Each thread utilizes a unique pruning vector that selectively enables or disables a different set of specific intermediate LUTs.

Algorithm 1 GPU-Based Greedy Prune Optimization.

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1:  $P_{id} \leftarrow \text{GetPruneVector}(\text{ThreadID}, \text{Threshold})$ 
2: for all  $S \in \text{StimulusVector}$  do
3:    $Inputs \leftarrow In(S)$ 
4:   for  $i = 0$  to  $N$  do
5:      $Lut_i \leftarrow P_{id}(i)?Eq_i : \{0, 1\}$ 
6:   end for
7:    $Out \leftarrow \text{ComputeIntermediate}(Lut)$ 
8:    $error \leftarrow error + \text{Distance}(Out, \text{Orig}(S))$ 
9: end for
10:  $totalError(\text{ThreadID}) \leftarrow error$ 

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Fig. 2: Pseudo-code for GPU-based Greedy pruning

Each thread evaluates a different pruning configuration against the entire stimulus vector and calculates the Hamming distance (or an alternative metric) to quantify accuracy degradation. Figure 2 illustrates this process through pseudo-code. In line 5, each thread selectively replaces the local function with 0 or 1, where $P_{id}(i)$ represents the random vector for LUT _{i} from thread id . Each thread thus performs a distinct evaluation, from which we select the optimal result. We use a pruning threshold P as a parameter. For example, in a circuit with 100 LUTs and $P = 10\%$, 10 LUTs will be set to 0 or 1, while 90 LUTs retain their original function.

V. RESULTS

Our experiments use the following configurations: CPU - Intel i5-12400F, 2.5 GHz, and 32 GB; and a GPU - NVIDIA RTX4060 8GB. To map the circuit to the LUT level, we used Yosys [26] and ABC~ [27] to perform the optimization script

“compress2rs”, and generate the final LUT-level circuit, with maximum LUT size of 4.

Table I shows the simulation execution time for the IS-CAS85 combinational circuit [28], a widespread benchmark set. We compare our Go-Fast simulator approach to the state-of-the-art Verilator simulator [20] that is used as a baseline for evaluating our multi-core CPU and GPU-based simulators. We simulate 2^{30} input value stimulus. For the GPU, we launched 768 blocks of 256 threads each, and each thread computes 171 stimuli. In the Go-Fast CPU implementation, we launched 12 threads, each processing 4 million stimuli, for approximately 2^{30} . While previous work on Verilog GPU-based present speed-up ranges from two, up to four orders of magnitude [14], [29], [30] compared to single core Verilator, our domain-specific simulator reaches five orders of magnitude in comparison to multi-core Verilator.

TABLE I: Execution time and throughput (sample/s) for ISCAS85 benchmarks: Verilator vs Go-Fast CPU and GPU.

Bench	LUTs	Gofast GPU Time (ms)	Throughput (sample/s)		
			Verilator	CPU Gofast	GPU Gofast
c1355	86	6.47	3.26×10^5	1.39×10^9	1.66×10^{11}
c1908	132	5.47	2.95×10^5	1.33×10^9	1.96×10^{11}
c3540	350	9.91	1.53×10^5	6.80×10^8	1.08×10^{11}
c432	77	4.83	5.08×10^5	1.51×10^9	2.22×10^{11}
c499	88	6.50	3.89×10^5	1.24×10^9	1.65×10^{11}
c5315	486	19.48	2.18×10^5	2.78×10^8	5.51×10^{10}
c6288	495	20.45	5.23×10^4	4.36×10^8	5.25×10^{10}
Average Speedup			1	4.15×10^3	5.72×10^5

The average Verilator execution time for a testbench size of 1.07 billion stimuli is around one hour, while our GPU-based implementation requires, on average, 12 milliseconds. The GPU-based simulator RTLFlow [14], using an A6000 GPU with 10572 cores, is around 100× in comparison to Verilator using 16 thread multi-core CPU (16th-CPU). TarotTL [31] uses CPU and GPU to improve RTLFlow by an average of 2×. Even ASH [29], a tailored chip hardware-based accelerator for RTL simulation with 256 cores, is around 100× faster than Verilator in a 16 th-CPU.

TABLE II: Execution time/throughput for EPFL benchmarks [32]: Verilator (16k stimulus) vs Go-Fast (2Gb stimulus).

Bench	LUTs	Gofast GPU Time (ms)	Throughput (sample/s)		
			Verilator	CPU	GO-FAST
adder	250	20.67	2.54×10^6	2.28×10^8	5.19×10^{10}
bar	896	21.79	1.59×10^5	4.86×10^8	4.93×10^{10}
log2	9172	889.69	2.08×10^4	2.34×10^7	1.21×10^9
multiplier	7105	2351.057	1.61×10^4	2.21×10^7	4.57×10^8
sin	1644	39.54	4.57×10^1	1.52×10^8	2.72×10^{10}
square	5532	2719.08	2.15×10^4	3.86×10^7	3.95×10^8
Geometric Mean Speedup			1	3.70×10^3	2.20×10^5

Table II presents the results for the EPFL combinational circuits [32], which include instances ranging from 250 up to 9,000 LUTs, compatible with actual implementations for edge devices [21], [22]. For Verilator, we sample only 2^{14} input stimuli due to the long simulation time. In contrast, Go-Fast

simulates 2^{30} input stimuli and is five orders of magnitude faster than Verilator.

Fig. 3: LUT Removal for c880 using a regression error.

The error metric could rely on regression with different bit weights or classification for approximate computing. Figure 3 depicts a box plot showing the error rate of 190K configurations as a function of the pruning rate or LUT removal percentage. We applied a regression bit-weighted metric on the 9-bit ALU output for the C880. The horizontal axis represents the LUT removal percentage, and the vertical axis represents the error rate, where lower is better. The best configuration appears as an outlier, shown by the dotted line at the bottom, achieving pruning of over 40% of the original 127 LUTs while maintaining an upper error bound of 5%. Furthermore, most of the 190K random configurations exhibit high error rates, with the median value at 40% pruning showing an error rate of approximately 30%.

These results demonstrate that even a naive random design exploration can achieve substantial pruning due to the performance advantages of the Go-Fast simulator. However, for classification problems where a single bit flip at the output constitutes an error, the maximum pruning for a 5% error rate is drastically reduced, representing a significantly more challenging constraint.

Fig. 4 presents box plots illustrating the LUT pruning process for 4 circuits from the ISCAS85 (c432, c880, c1908, and c2670) with an upper error bound of 5% for a classification metric. On the left, we compute the error rate considering an input stimulus of 2^{21} , while on the right of Fig. 4, the stimulus size is 2^{14} . First, Go-Fast enables the evaluation of pruning over a larger stimulus size, which is crucial for validating optimal pruning. Second, although the left and right sides exhibit similar shapes for a given circuit, the error rate appears smaller on the right side since it is measured over a reduced stimulus set of 2^{14} . Most approximate approaches in the literature use stimulus sizes of around 2^{13} to reduce simulation requirements, and Go-Fast solves it by providing a high-performance simulator. Third, when comparing the regression and classification results for C880, it becomes evident how challenging pruning becomes when using more rigorous metrics. With classification metrics, we can reduce the circuit by only 5%, while regression allows up to 40%

Fig. 4: Classification Error Rate vs. LUT removal for 190K configurations. The dashline is the best configuration.

reduction, as shown in Fig. 3 by relaxing the error metric.

TABLE III: LUT Pruning using Go-Fast and ResubALS [2].

Bench	Number of LUT-4				FINAL PRUNE
	Original	Go-Fast	Resub	Go-Fast → Resub	
c1908	132	86	44	43	67%
c2670	290	234	221	216	26%
c432	77	49	51	48	38%
c880	127	104	87	85	33%

Finally, we evaluated pruning using a naive approach based on random stuck-at-0/1 faults, as our goal is to demonstrate the feasibility of integrating simulation and pruning on GPU. We compared the pruning results to ResubALS, one of the state-of-the-art of ALS [2]. Tab. III presents the results obtained using Go-Fast and ResubALS [2]. We evaluated three approaches: Go-Fast, ResubALS, and Go-Fast + ResubALS. The error upper bound was fixed at 5% using a classification metric. For C2670 and C432, even with a naive pruning

approach, Go-Fast achieved results comparable to ResubALS. For C1908 and C880, applying naive pruning followed by ResubALS enabled a further reduction in circuit size. The final LUT reduction ranged from 26% to 67%.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents a novel GPU simulator that is five orders of magnitude faster than Verilator [20], and one to two orders of magnitude faster than state-of-the-art simulators [14], [29], [31] by exploiting domain-specific LUT circuits and GPU's more-work-per-thread approach [17]. As a case study, we integrate an approximate logic naive pruning approach. Future work will extend this to incorporate state-of-the-art approximate logic synthesis techniques [2] targeting machine learning implementations using LUT-based FPGAs [21], [22]. Go-Fast can simulate more than 10 billion samples per second, enabling validation of pruning/accuracy relationships for large stimulus sizes to develop ML edge devices.

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